

A Study on Effects of Television Advertisement on Consumer Buying Behaviour

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Abstract- Television advertising plays a significant role in shaping consumer buying behavior by influencing awareness, attitudes, and purchase decisions. This study examines the effect of television advertisements on consumers by analyzing how visual appeal, message content, repetition, celebrity endorsements, and emotional elements impact buying intentions. Television advertisements act as a powerful communication tool that not only informs consumers about products and services but also persuades them by creating brand recall and positive perceptions. The study highlights that frequent exposure to television advertisements increases product familiarity and trust, which in turn affects consumers' preferences and choice of brands. Moreover, advertisements targeting emotions and lifestyles are found to be more effective in motivating impulse buying and brand loyalty. The findings suggest that television advertising continues to be an influential factor in consumer decision-making, despite the growth of digital media, and remains a crucial strategy for marketers to attract, influence, and retain consumers in competitive markets.

Keywords: Advertisement, media, purchasing behavior, Buying Intentions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Television advertising has long been one of the most powerful and widely used promotional tools for influencing consumer buying behaviour. With its ability to combine visual images, sound, motion, and persuasive messages, television advertisements effectively capture the attention of a large and diverse audience. In everyday life, consumers are constantly exposed to advertisements that inform them about new products, remind them of existing brands, and shape their perceptions and preferences. These advertisements not only create awareness but also influence attitudes, emotions, and purchasing decisions. The effect of television advertising is especially significant as it reaches consumers repeatedly, builds brand recall, and establishes trust through consistent messaging. Even in the era of digital marketing, television continues to play a vital role in affecting consumer choices,

making it an important area of study for understanding consumer buying behaviour and marketing strategies.

OBJECTIVES

- To determine the effects of advertisements on television on the buying decision of people.
- To examine how TV advertisements affect consumer attitudes and responses.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The rapid growth of digital media, television advertising continues to remain a dominant promotional tool for influencing consumer decisions. However, it is not clearly understood to what extent television advertisement shape consumer buying behaviour in terms of awareness, preferences, brand recall, and purchase decisions. Many consumers are exposed to repetitive and persuasive tv ads, yet their actual buying responses appeal, frequency of exposure, credibility of the advertisement and personal preferences. This raises a critical question about the real effectiveness of television advertisement in motivating consumers to choose one product over another. Therefore, the problem addressed in this study is to examine identifying advertisements that affect consumer buying behaviour and to identify the specific advertising elements that significantly influence purchase intentions.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The study relies on participants self-reported perceptions and behaviour which may be influenced by bias or inaccurate recall.
2. Consumers mainly focused on the program tv advertisements are watched slightly lesser than normal nowadays.
3. The research focuses only on tv advertisements, ignoring the possible influence of other social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Belch and Belch (2015) The studied the role of television advertising in influencing consumer buying behaviour. The authors found that television advertisements are effective in creating brand awareness and improving brand recall among consumers. Their study highlighted that repeated exposure to TV advertisements helps consumers remember product features and brand names, which later influences their purchase decisions. Emotional appeals, visuals, and persuasive messages used in TV advertisements were found to strongly affect consumers' attitudes and buying intentions.

Kotler and Keller (2016) The article examined how advertising acts as a powerful promotional tool in shaping consumer perceptions and preferences. According to their study, television advertisements significantly influence consumers by combining audio and visual elements that attract attention and create interest. The authors emphasized that television advertising plays an important role in influencing consumer emotions, building trust, and encouraging trial purchases, especially for fast-moving consumer goods.

Shimp (2014) This study analysed the impact of persuasive and emotional content in television advertisements on consumer behaviour. The study revealed that advertisements using celebrities, storytelling, music, and emotional themes are more effective in influencing consumers attitudes towards brands. Shimp concluded that television advertisements not only inform consumers about products but also persuade them by creating positive feelings, which ultimately leads to higher purchase intention.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopts a descriptive research design to examine the effect of television advertisement on the consumer buying behaviour. This design is suitable as it helps in describing and analysing the existing opinions, attitudes, and behavioural patterns of the respondents.

Sample size

The study was conducted among 110 respondents representing different demographic groups with the population.

Sampling Tools

Data were collected using structured questionnaires and survey forms, which enabled the researcher to gather reliable and relevant information about the effects of television advertisements on the consumer buying behaviour. The collected data were analysed using chi square analysis to interpret responses and identify trends.

Area of the Study:

The research was conducted among the youth in Coimbatore City, Tamil Nadu, which is one of the fastest growing urban centres in South India. Coimbatore is not only an educational hub but also commercial and industrial city. The city has a vibrant youth population. This makes it an appropriate setting to study the impact on Effects of Television Advertisement on consumer Buying Behaviour, as the respondents represent diverse demographic backgrounds and consumption patterns influenced by tv advertisements trends. The study focused on youths between the age groups of below 18 up to 32 years.

Methods of Data Collection

Primary Data

Primary data is firsthand information collected directly by the researcher using tools such as surveys and questionnaires.

Secondary Data

Secondary data is information collected previously by other sources and is available in published formats. The secondary data collected for the study from various Journals, magazines, books, newspapers, reports, and online articles.

IV. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- Male respondents significantly outnumbered females, constituting 73.64% versus 26.36% respectively.
- Majority of the respondents fall in the age group of 18 -25 90%.
- Most of the respondents are under graduate students 87.27%
- Students dominated the occupation category at 86.36%, while employees constituted 7.27% and home maker consists of only 2.73%
- 90.91% of the respondents are part time working with the income category of below 10000 and most of them are students and 9.09% income category of above 10000
- 100% of the respondents lives in urban areas.

- 65.45% of the respondents are strongly agree that influence television advertisement to buy a product.
- 56.36% of the respondents were told very helpful shown in tv ads help us to make a decision on purchase.
- 73.64% of the respondents are strongly agreed tv advertisement increase the interest in a product.
- 48.18% of the respondents are strongly agreed emotional content in tv ads changes the consumer attitude toward a product.
- 66.36% of the respondents were agreed persuasive messages are think positively about the product.
- 70.33% of the respondents are strongly agreed about the music and background sounds in TV ads improves the attitude towards the brand.
- 60.91% of the respondents are strongly agreed about the real-life situations affect the attitude more than simple product TV ads.
- 48.18% of the respondents were very much agreed about TV advertisements influence the preference for one brand over another.
- 52.73% of the respondents were strongly agreed celebrity endorsement in TV ads affect the interest in the product.
- Around 70.91% of the respondents are agrees that TV advertisements increase the trust in a product or brand.
- Around 70.55% of the respondents very much agreed television advertisements influence their buying decisions.

Chi Square Analysis

- To Analyse the relationship between the age of respondents and their perception of emotional content in TV advertisements. The calculated p-value is 0.000000397 which is less than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant relationship between age and perception of emotional content in TV ads.
- The test was conducted to examine the relationship between the educational level of respondents and their perception of persuasive messages in TV advertisements. The calculated p-value 0.8589 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant relationship between educational level and the perception of persuasive messages.
- The test was conducted to determine the relationship between the occupation of respondents and the influence of television advertisements on their buying decisions. The calculated Chi- p-value 0.035 is less than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant relationship between

occupation and the influence of TV advertisements on buying decisions.

V. SUGGESTION

Advertisers should use creative and interesting content in TV ads since television advertisements significantly increase consumer interest in product. More emphasis should be given to emotional appeal in advertisements, as emotional content has a strong impact on changing consumer attitudes toward products. Brands should design persuasive and clear messages in TV advertisements, as persuasive communication helps consumers think positively about products. The use of appropriate music and background sounds should be encouraged, because it improves consumer attitude toward the brand. Advertisements should include real-life situations and relatable scenarios, as they influence consumer attitudes more effectively than simple product-focused ads. Careful use of celebrity endorsements can be adopted, since celebrities in TV advertisements positively affect consumer interest, brand preference, and trust. Advertisements should focus on honest information and clear product benefits to maintain consumer confidence.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that television advertising continues to play a significant role in influencing consumer buying behaviour despite the increasing presence of digital media. Television advertisements are effective in creating product awareness, improving brand recall, and shaping consumer preferences, which in turn influence purchase intentions. Repetitive exposure to television advertisements helps consumers remember brands and associate. Marketers should therefore focus on creating credible, engaging, a consumer-oriented television advertisements to enhance their effectiveness in influencing buying behaviour.

APPENDIX

Appendixes, if needed, appear before the acknowledgement

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The preferred spelling of the word acknowledgement in American English is without. Use the singular headings even if you have many acknowledgements.

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